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On Bounds of Non-Deficient Numbers

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Abstract

Objectives: To improve the upper bounds of a quasi perfect number and give an important result on its divisibility with primes. **Methods:** A positive integer n is quasi perfect if $\sigma(n) > 2n + 1$, where $\sigma(n)$ denotes the sum of the positive divisors of n . However, the existence of a quasi perfect number, which is a Non-Deficient number, is still an open problem. We use $R(n)$, the sum of the reciprocals of distinct primes dividing the quasi perfect number, to derive lemmas and improve the bounds obtained by earlier authors. **Findings:** We improve the upper bounds for $R(n)$, when n is quasi perfect with $\gcd(15, n) = 3$ or $\gcd(15, n) = 5$. As a consequence, we establish that a quasi perfect number, if exists, is divisible by both 3 and 5 or by none of them. **Novelty:** The unique method of using $R(n)$ also resulted in finding an important result that 3, 5 and 7 cannot divide any quasi perfect number.

Mathematics Subject Classification: 11A05, 11A25

Keywords: non-deficient number; quasi perfect number; sum of the divisor; sum of the reciprocal; bounds of perfect number; number of divisors.

1 Introduction

let $\sigma(n)$ denote the sum of the positive divisors of n . It is well-known that a positive integer n is said to be abundant, perfect or deficient according as $\sigma(n) > 2n$, $\sigma(n) = 2n$ or $\sigma(n) < 2n$. One can see that the set of abundant numbers as well as the set of deficient numbers are both infinite. In fact, the numbers of the form $2^k \cdot 3$ with $k > 1$ are all abundant, while every prime is deficient. But it is not known whether the set of perfect numbers is infinite or not.

Cattaneo⁽¹⁾ has called a positive integer n quasi perfect if $\sigma(n) = 2n + 1$. It is not known whether such numbers exist at all. Abbott, Kishore and Cohen⁽²⁻⁵⁾ have made significant contributions to the study of quasi perfect numbers. In 1978, Kishore⁽⁴⁾ used the inequality $2 - 10^{-12} < \sigma(N)/N < 2 + 10^{-12}$ and proved that there are no odd perfect numbers, no quasi perfect numbers and no odd almost perfect numbers with five distinct prime factors, proving $\omega(n) \geq 6$, where $\omega(n)$ denotes number of divisors of n .

Cohen⁽⁶⁾ proved, if any quasi perfect number n exists, then

$$(1.1.1) \omega(n) \geq 7 \text{ and } n > 10^{35}$$

Subsequently, Peter Hagis and Cohen⁽⁷⁾ have used computations to improve some of the results on quasi perfect numbers. In fact, they established that

(1.1.2) for any quasi perfect number n , $\omega(n) \geq 15$ if $(15, n) = 1$, $\omega(n) \geq 9$ if $3 \nmid n$ and in other case $\omega(n) > 7$ and also $n > 10^{35}$, where $\omega(n)$ denotes the number of divisors of n .

Cattaneo⁽¹⁾ has proved the following theorem:

1.1 **Theorem:** If n is a quasi perfect number then

(1.1.3) $n = p_1^{2e_1} p_2^{2e_2} \dots p_r^{2e_r}$

where p_i 's are odd primes

Moreover,

(1.1.4) i) $p_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8} \Rightarrow e_i \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{4}$

ii) $p_i \equiv 3 \pmod{8} \Rightarrow e_i \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$

iii) $p_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8} \Rightarrow e_i \equiv 0 \text{ or } -1 \pmod{4}$

iv) $p_i \equiv 7 \pmod{8} \Rightarrow e_i \geq 1$

In a different direction, Cohen⁽⁸⁾ has considered $R(n)$, the sum of the reciprocals of the distinct primes dividing the quasi perfect number n (if exists) and obtained bounds for $R(n)$. They are

(1.1.5)

i) $0.667450 < R(n) < 0.693148$ if $(15, n) = 1$

ii) $0.603831 < R(n) < 0.625140$ if $(15, n) = 3$

iii) $0.647387 < R(n) < 0.670017$ if $(15, n) = 5$

iv) $0.596063 < R(n) < 0.602009$ if $(15, n) = 15$

New methods were introduced by Tang and Feng⁽⁹⁾ and they established that there are no odd deficient-perfect numbers with three distinct prime divisors. The alternate proof was given in⁽¹⁰⁾ using special components, which is

(1.1.6) If n is a quasi perfect number and is of the form (1.1.3) then for at least one factor $p_i^{2e_i}$, we have either

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} p_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8} \text{ and } e_i \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ \text{or} \\ p_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8} \text{ and } e_i \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \end{array} \right)$$

Calling $p_i^{2e_i}$ as a special component if it satisfies (1.1.6)

and proved every quasi perfect number has an odd number of special components.

In 2019, Tomohiro⁽¹¹⁾ has given some lower bounds concerning quasi perfect numbers of the form $N = m^2$ where m is square free and Prasad⁽¹²⁾ obtained a lower bound for the product of the distinct primes dividing n in terms of $\omega(n)$.

In this paper, the upper bounds given in (1.1.5) are improved and subsequently an important result regarding divisibility with primes of n is obtained.

2 Methodology

In this section, we will prove some lemmas used in the sequel. We shall give detailed proof of the required lemmas in⁽¹³⁾ which were used for bounds of odd perfect numbers.

2.1 Lemma:

For $0 < p \leq \frac{1}{3}$ we have $1 + p + p^2 + p^3 + p^4 > e^{p+t_1 p^2}$ where $t_1 = 0.373$.

Proof: For simplicity of notation we write t for t_1 . Consider the function

$$f(p) = e^{(p+tp^2)-(1+p+p^2+p^3+p^4)}$$

$$= \left(1 + \frac{(p+tp^2)}{1!} + \frac{(p+tp^2)^2}{2!} + \frac{(p+tp^2)^3}{3!} + \dots \right) - (1 + p + p^2 + p^3 + p^4)$$

$$= p^2 \left(t - \frac{1}{2} \right) + p^3 (t - 1) + p^4 \left(\frac{t^2}{2} - 1 \right) + \frac{1}{3!} (p + tp^2)^3 + \dots$$

Now the inequality of the lemma holds

$$\Leftrightarrow f(p) < 0$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{3!} (p + tp^2)^3 + \frac{1}{4!} (p + tp^2)^4 + \dots < p^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} - t \right) + p^3 (1 - t) + p^4 \left(1 - \frac{t^2}{2} \right)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{3!}p(1+tp)^3 + \frac{1}{4!}p^2(1+tp)^4 + \dots < \left(\frac{1}{2}-t\right) + p(1-t) + p^2\left(1-\frac{t^2}{2}\right)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{6}p(1+tp)^3 \left(1 + \frac{1}{4}p(1+tp) + \dots\right) < \left(\frac{1}{2}-t\right) \tag{1}$$

But for $0 < p \leq \frac{1}{3}$, we have

$$g(p) = \frac{1}{6}p(1+tp)^3 \left(1 + \frac{1}{4}p(1+tp) + \frac{1}{20}p^2(1+tp)^2 + \dots\right)$$

$$< \frac{1}{6}p(1+tp)^3 \left(1 + (p+tp^2) + (p+tp^2)^2 + \dots\right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{6}p(1+tp)^3 [1 - (p+tp^2)]^{-1},$$

Whenever t is chosen such that $(p+tp^2) < 1$. Therefore for $0 < p \leq \frac{1}{3}$, we have

$$g(p) < \frac{1}{6}p(1+tp)^3 \left(\frac{1}{1-(p+tp^2)}\right)$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{18} \left(1 + \frac{t}{3}\right)^3 \left(\frac{1}{1-\left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{t}{9}\right)}\right)$$

$$\frac{1}{18} \bullet \frac{(3+t)^3}{3^3} \bullet \frac{9}{6-t} \tag{2}$$

Now from (1) and (2), the inequality of the lemma holds if

$$\frac{1}{18} \bullet \frac{(3+t)^3}{3^3} \bullet \frac{9}{6-t} < \frac{1}{2} - t,$$

and this holds for $t = 0.373$. Hence the lemma.

In similar way, we can prove the following Lemma 2.2, Lemma 2.3 and Lemma 2.4.

2.2 Lemma:

For $0 < p \leq \frac{1}{7}$ we have $1 + p + p^2 > e^{p+t_2p^2}$ where $t_2 = 0.406$.

2.3 Lemma:

For $0 < p \leq \frac{1}{5}$ we have $1 + p + p^2 + p^3 + p^4 + p^5 + p^6 > e^{(p+t_3p^2)}$ Where $t_3 = 0.496$

2.4 Lemma:

For $0 < p \leq \frac{1}{5}$ we have $1 + p + p^2 + p^3 + p^4 + p^5 + p^6 + p^7 + p^8 > e^{(p+t_4p^2)}$ Where $t_4 = 0.4998$.

2.5 Lemma:

Suppose p is a quasi perfect number, $R_k(p)$ is the sum of reciprocals of the k^{th} powers of the distinct primes dividing p and $t = \min(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4) = 0.373$ where t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4 are as given in Lemma 2.1 to 2.4. Then $R_1(p) + cR_2(p) < \log(2.000000001)$.

Proof: Given that p is quasiperfect, so that in view of (1.1.3) and (1.1.6) we can write p as

(2.5.1)

$$p = a_1^{2e_1} a_2^{2e_2} \dots a_r^{2e_r} \cdot b_1^{2f_1} b_2^{2f_2} \dots b_s^{2f_s}$$

Where each of the $a_i^{2e_i}$ is a special component and $b_j^{2f_j}$ is any component.

Then by (1.1.6), r is odd and also for each i , we have either

(2.5.2)

$$\begin{cases} a_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8} & \text{and } e_i \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ \text{or} \\ a_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8} & \text{and } e_i \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \end{cases}$$

Further by (1.1.4), for each j ,

(2.5.3)

$$(2.5.3) \quad \begin{cases} b_j \equiv 1 \pmod{8} \Rightarrow f_j \equiv 0 \pmod{4} \\ b_j \equiv 3 \pmod{8} \Rightarrow f_j \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ b_j \equiv 5 \pmod{8} \Rightarrow f_j \equiv 0 \pmod{4} \\ b_j \equiv 7 \pmod{8} \Rightarrow f_j \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

Therefore by (2.5.2) and (2.5.3) we have

(2.5.4)

$$\begin{aligned} 2 + \frac{1}{p} &= \frac{\sigma(p)}{p} = \prod_{i=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{a_i} + \dots + \frac{1}{a_i^{2e_i}} \right) \prod_{j=1}^s \left(1 + \frac{1}{b_j} + \dots + \frac{1}{b_j^{2f_j}} \right) \\ &> \prod_{a_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{a_i} + \frac{1}{a_i^2} \right) \prod_{a_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{a_i} + \frac{1}{a_i^2} + \frac{1}{a_i^3} + \frac{1}{a_i^4} + \frac{1}{a_i^5} + \frac{1}{a_i^6} \right) \\ &\quad \prod_{b_j \equiv 1 \pmod{8}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{b_j} + \frac{1}{b_j^2} + \frac{1}{b_j^3} + \frac{1}{b_j^4} + \frac{1}{b_j^5} + \frac{1}{b_j^6} + \frac{1}{b_j^7} + \frac{1}{b_j^8} \right) \\ &\quad \prod_{b_j \equiv 3 \pmod{8}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{b_j} + \frac{1}{b_j^2} + \frac{1}{b_j^3} + \frac{1}{b_j^4} \right) \cdot \prod_{b_j \equiv 7 \pmod{8}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{b_j} + \frac{1}{b_j^2} \right) \\ &\quad \prod_{b_j \equiv 5 \pmod{8}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{b_j} + \frac{1}{b_j^2} + \frac{1}{b_j^3} + \frac{1}{b_j^4} + \frac{1}{b_j^5} + \frac{1}{b_j^6} + \frac{1}{b_j^7} + \frac{1}{b_j^8} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Now using Lemmas 2.1 to 2.4 on the right of (2.5.4) we get

$$\begin{aligned} 2 + \frac{1}{p} &> \prod_{a_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}} e^{\left(\frac{1}{a_i} + \frac{t_1}{a_i^2} \right)} \cdot \prod_{a_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8}} e^{\left(\frac{1}{a_i} + \frac{t_3}{a_i^2} \right)} \cdot \prod_{b_j \equiv 1 \pmod{8}} e^{\left(\frac{1}{b_j} + \frac{t_4}{b_j^2} \right)} \cdot \prod_{b_j \equiv 3 \pmod{8}} e^{\left(\frac{1}{b_j} + \frac{t_2}{b_j^2} \right)} \\ &\quad \cdot \prod_{b_j \equiv 5 \pmod{8}} e^{\left(\frac{1}{b_j} + \frac{t_4}{b_j^2} \right)} \cdot \prod_{b_j \equiv 7 \pmod{8}} e^{\left(\frac{1}{b_j} + \frac{t_1}{b_j^2} \right)} \end{aligned}$$

Which on taking logarithm gives

$$\log \left(2 + \frac{1}{n} \right) > \sum_{a_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}} \left(\frac{1}{a_i} + \frac{t_1}{a_i^2} \right) + \sum_{a_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8}} \left(\frac{1}{a_i} + \frac{t_3}{a_i^2} \right) + \sum_{b_j \equiv 1 \pmod{8}} \left(\frac{1}{q_j} + \frac{t_4}{q_j^2} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \sum_{b_j \equiv 3 \pmod{8}} \left(\frac{1}{q_j} + \frac{t_2}{q_j^2} \right) + \sum_{b_j \equiv 5 \pmod{8}} \left(\frac{1}{q_j} + \frac{t_4}{q_j^2} \right) + \sum_{b_j \equiv 7 \pmod{8}} \left(\frac{1}{q_j} + \frac{t_1}{q_j^2} \right) \\
 = & R_1(p) + t_1 \sum_{a_i \equiv 1 \pmod{8}} \frac{1}{a_i^2} + t_3 \sum_{a_i \equiv 5 \pmod{8}} \frac{1}{a_i^2} + t_4 \sum_{b_j \equiv 1 \pmod{8}} \frac{1}{b_j^2} \\
 & + t_2 \sum_{b_j \equiv 3 \pmod{8}} \frac{1}{q_j^2} + t_4 \sum_{b_j \equiv 5 \pmod{8}} \frac{1}{q_j^2} + t_4 \sum_{b_j \equiv 7 \pmod{8}} \frac{1}{q_j^2} \\
 > & R_1(p) + tR_2(p) \\
 \text{Since } t = & \min(t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4), \text{ proving the lemma because } p > 10^{35}.
 \end{aligned}$$

2.6 Lemma:

Suppose p is quasi perfect and $\alpha = 2 + \frac{1}{p}$. Then for any divisor of q of p with $q < p$, we have $R_1(p) < R_1(q) + tR_2(q) + \log\left(\frac{\alpha q}{\beta \sigma(q)}\right) - tR_2(p)$, where $\beta = 1$ if $(p, 15) = 1$ or $(p, 15) = (q, 15) = 3$ or $(p, 15) = (q, 15) = 5$ or $(p, 15) = (q, 15) = 15$
 $1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2}$ if $(p, 15) = 3$ and $(q, 15) = 1$ or $(p, 15) = 15$ and $(q, 15) = 5$
 $1 + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{5^2}$ if $(p, 15) = 5$ and $(q, 15) = 1$ or $(p, 15) = 15$ and $(q, 15) = 3$
 $\left(1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{5^2}\right)$ if $(p, 15) = 15$ and $(q, 15) = 1$

Proof: Suppose p is quasiperfect, it is of the form $p = \prod_{i=1}^r a_i^{2e_i}$, where a_i 's are odd primes, then
(2.6.1)

$$\alpha = 2 + \frac{1}{p} = \frac{\sigma(p)}{p} = \prod_{i=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{a_i} + \frac{1}{a_i^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{a_i^{2e_i}} \right)$$

Suppose $q = \prod_{i=1}^r a_i^{b_i}$ is a divisor of p with $q < p$. Then $0 \leq b_i \leq 2e_i$ for each i and $b_i < 2e_i$ for at least one i . Also
(2.6.2)

$$\frac{\sigma(q)}{q} = \prod_{i=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i} + \frac{1}{p_i^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{p_i^{b_i}} \right)$$

Now from (2.6.1), (2.6.2) and Lemma 2.1, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \geq \prod_{\substack{i=1 \\ a_i|q}}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{a_i} + \dots + \frac{1}{a_i^{b_i}} \right) \prod_{\substack{i=1 \\ a_i \nmid q}}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{a_i} + \dots + \frac{1}{a_i^{2e_i}} \right) \\
 = & \frac{\sigma(q)}{q} \exp \left\{ \sum_{a|p} \left(\frac{1}{a} + t \cdot \frac{1}{a^2} \right) \right\} \cdot \beta \\
 \text{Which on taking logarithm gives} \\
 \log \alpha & > \log \left(\frac{\sigma(q)}{q} \right) + \sum_{\substack{a|p \\ a \nmid q}} \left(\frac{1}{a} + t \cdot \frac{1}{a^2} \right) + \log \beta \\
 = & \log \left(\frac{\sigma(q)}{q} \right) + \sum_{a|q} \frac{1}{a} + t \cdot \sum_{a|p} \frac{1}{a^2} + \log \beta \\
 & \log \left(\frac{\sigma(q)}{q} \right) + R_1(p) - R_1(q) + t(R_2(p) - R_2(q)) + \log \beta
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_1(p) & < R_1(q) + \log \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right) - \log \left(\frac{\sigma(q)}{q} \right) - t(R_2(p) - R_2(q)) \\
 = & R_1(q) + tR_2(q) + \log \left(\frac{\alpha(q)}{\beta \sigma(q)} \right) - tR_2(p) \\
 \text{Proving the lemma.}
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Theorem:

Suppose $3 \mid n$ and $5 \nmid n$. Then

i) $R_1(n) < 0.2727439241$ if $7 \mid n$.
and

ii) $R_1(n) < 0.2839779561$ if $7 \nmid n$.

Proof: (i) Suppose $3 \mid n$ and $7 \mid n$.

It was proved in (2) that if $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ is a divisor of n then $p^k \mid n$ with $k \geq 4$. Therefore $7^4 \mid n$. Also since $w(n) \geq 7$ we get that $m = 7^4$ is a divisor of n with $m < n$, so that by Lemma 2.6 we have

$$\begin{aligned} R_1(n) &< R_1(m) + cR_2(m) + \log\left(\frac{\alpha m}{\beta \sigma(m)}\right) - cR_2(n) \\ &= \frac{1}{7} + 0.373\left(\frac{1}{7^2}\right) + \log\left(\frac{\alpha \cdot 7^4 \cdot 6}{\beta \cdot (7^5 - 1)}\right) - (0.373)\left(\frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{7^2}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{7} + 0.373\left(\frac{1}{7^2}\right) + \log\alpha + \log\left(\frac{7^4 \cdot 6}{(1.444444444) \cdot (7^5 - 1)}\right) - (0.373)\left(\frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{7^2}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{7} + 0.373\left(\frac{1}{7^2}\right) + \log 2 + \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2n}\right) + \log\left(\frac{14406}{24275.33333}\right) - (0.373)\left(\frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{7^2}\right) \\ &= 0.272743924 + \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2n}\right) \\ &= 0.272743924 + 0.0000000001, \text{ since } n > 10^{35}. \text{ Thus } R_1(n) < 0.2727439241. \end{aligned}$$

Suppose $3 \mid n$ and $7 \nmid n$

It follows from (1.1.4) (ii) that $3^4 \mid n$. Also let $m = 1$ is a divisor of n with $m < n$, so that by Lemma 2.6 we have $R_1(n) < \log\left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta}\right) - cR_2(n)$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \log\alpha - \log\beta - (0.373)\left(\frac{1}{3^2}\right) \\ &= \log 2 + \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2n}\right) - \log(1.444444444) - (0.373)\left(\frac{1}{3^2}\right) \\ &= 0.283977956 + \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2n}\right) \\ &= 0.283977956 + 0.0000000001, \text{ since } n > 10^{35}. \text{ Thus } R_1(n) < 0.2839779561. \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Theorem:

Suppose $3 \mid n$ and $5 \mid n$. Then

i) $R_1(n) < 0.4547419741$ if $7 \mid n$.
and

ii) $R_1(n) < 0.4631158001$ if $7 \nmid n$

Proof: (i) Suppose $5 \mid n$ and $7 \mid n$.

It follows from (1.1.4) (iii) and (1.1.4) (iv) that $5^6 \mid n$ and $7^2 \mid n$. Also since $w(n) \geq 7$ we get that $m = 7^2$ is a divisor of n with $m < n$, so that by Lemma 2.6 we have

$$\begin{aligned} R_1(n) &< R_1(m) + cR_2(m) + \log\left(\frac{\alpha m}{\beta \sigma(m)}\right) - cR_2(n) \\ &= \frac{1}{7} + 0.373\left(\frac{1}{7^2}\right) + \log\left(\frac{\alpha \cdot 7^2 \cdot 6}{\beta \cdot (7^3 - 1)}\right) - (0.373)\left(\frac{1}{5^2} + \frac{1}{7^2}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{7} + 0.373\left(\frac{1}{7^2}\right) + \log\alpha + \log\left(\frac{7^2 \cdot 6}{(1.24) \cdot (342)}\right) - (0.373)\left(\frac{1}{5^2} + \frac{1}{7^2}\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{7} + 0.373\left(\frac{1}{7^2}\right) + \log 2 + \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2n}\right) + \log\left(\frac{294}{424.08}\right) - (0.373)\left(\frac{1}{5^2} + \frac{1}{7^2}\right) \\ &= 0.454741974 + \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2n}\right) \\ &= 0.454741974 + 0.0000000001, \text{ since } n > 10^{35}. \text{ Thus } R_1(n) < 0.4547419741. \end{aligned}$$

Suppose $5 \mid n$ and $7 \nmid n$

It follows from (1.1.4) (iii) that $5^6 \mid n$. Also let $m = 1$ is a divisor of n with $m < n$, so that by Lemma 2.6 we have

$$\begin{aligned} R_1(n) &< \log\left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta}\right) - cR_2(n) \\ &= \log\alpha - \log\beta - (0.373)\left(\frac{1}{5^2}\right) \\ &= \log 2 + \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2n}\right) - \log(1.24) - (0.373)\left(\frac{1}{5^2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$= 0.4631158 + \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2n}\right)$$

$$= 0.4631158 + 0.0000000001, \text{ since } n > 10^{35}. \text{ Thus } R_1(n) < 0.4631158001.$$

3.3 Theorem:

If n is quasi perfect then $(15, n) = 1$ or 15 . More explicitly, every quasi perfect number is divisible by both 3 and 5 or by none of them.

Proof: If n is quasi perfect and $(15, n) = 3$.

Then by Lemma 3.1, $R_1(n) < 0.2839779561$ while $R_1(n) > 0.603831$ by (1.1.5) (ii), which gives a contradiction. Hence $(15, n) \neq 3$.

Again, if $(15, n) = 5$.

Then by Lemma 3.2, $R_1(n) < 0.4631158001$ while (1.1.5) (iii) gives $R_1(n) > 0.647387$. These two contradict each other. Hence $(15, n) \neq 5$.

Thus $(15, n) = 1$ or 15 , proving the theorem.

3.4 Theorem:

If n is quasi perfect then 3.5.7 cannot divide n .

Proof: Suppose 3.5.7 divide n . Then it follows from (1.1.4) (ii), (1.1.4) (iii) and (1.1.4) (iv) that $3^4 \mid n, 5^6 \mid n, 7^2 \mid n$. But it was proved in (2) that if $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ is a divisor of n then $pk \mid n$ with $k \geq 4$. Therefore $7^4 \mid n$. Also since $w(n) \geq 7$ we get that $m = 3^4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7^4$ is a divisor of n with $m < n$, so that by Lemma 2.6 we have

$$R_1(n) < R_1(m) + cR_2(m) + \log\left(\frac{\alpha m}{\beta \sigma(m)}\right) - cR_2(n)$$

$$= \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{7} + 0.373 \left(\frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{5^2} + \frac{1}{7^2} \right) + \log\left(\frac{\alpha \cdot 3^4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7^4 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6}{\beta \cdot (3^5 - 1) \cdot (5^7 - 1) \cdot (7^5 - 1)}\right) - (0.373) \left(\frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{5^2} + \frac{1}{7^2} \right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{7} + \log \alpha + \log\left(\frac{3^4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7^4 \cdot 48}{1 \cdot (3^5 - 1) \cdot (5^7 - 1) \cdot (7^5 - 1)}\right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{7} + \log 2 + \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2n}\right) + \log\left(\frac{3^4 \cdot 5^6 \cdot 7^4 \cdot 48}{(3^5 - 1) \cdot (5^7 - 1) \cdot (7^5 - 1)}\right)$$

$$= 0.590774338 + \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2n}\right)$$

$$= 0.590774338 + 0.0000000001, \text{ since } n > 10^{35}. \text{ Thus } R_1(n) < 0.5907743381.$$

But (1.1.5) (iv) gives $R_1(n) > 0.596063$, which gives a contradiction.

Hence 3.5.7 cannot divide n .

4 Conclusion

The study is focused on improving upper bounds and in the process concluding about the restrictions on divisors of quasi perfect numbers which is a non-deficient number. The inequality we proved in lemma 2.6 is used to improve bounds in Theorem 3.1 and Theorem 3.2 which helps in the important conclusion that either 3 and 5 together divide a quasi perfect number or none of them divide. We also come to the conclusion that 3.5.7 together cannot divide a quasi perfect number.

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